

Kinetics and mechanism of the oxidation of oxalic and formic acids by tetraethylammonium chlorochromate

Shilpa Pohani, Priyanka Purohit, Shweta Vyas and Pradeep K. Sharma*

Department of Chemistry, J. N. V. University, Jodhpur-342 005, Rajasthan, India

E-mail : drpkvs27@yahoo.com

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Abstract : Kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of formic and oxalic acids by tetraethylammonium chlorochromate (TEACC) have been studied in dimethylsulphoxide. The main product of oxidation is carbon dioxide. The reaction is first order with respect to TEACC and the organic acids. The reaction is acid-catalysed and the acid dependence has the form : $k_{\text{obs}} = a + b[\text{H}^+]$. The oxidation of α -deuterioformic acid exhibits a substantial primary kinetic isotope effect ($k_{\text{H}}/k_{\text{D}} = 5.83$ at 298 K). The reaction has been studied in nineteen different organic solvents and the solvent effect has been analysed using Taft's and Swain's multiparametric equations. The temperature dependence of the kinetic isotope effect indicates the presence of a symmetrical cyclic transition state in the rate-determining step. Suitable mechanisms have been proposed.

Keywords : Halochromate, kinetics, mechanism, oxidation, organic acids.

Introduction

Halochromates have long been used as specific, selective and mild oxidizing reagents in synthetic organic chemistry¹⁻⁵. Tetraethylammonium chlorochromate (TEACC) is also one such compound used for the oxidation benzyl alcohols⁶. There seems to be no report on the oxidation aspects using tetraethylammonium chlorochromate (TEACC). We have been interested in the kinetic and mechanistic aspects of the oxidation by complexed Cr^{VI} species and several studies by halochromates have already been reported⁷⁻¹⁰. Therefore, we report in the present article the kinetics of oxidation of oxalic and formic acids by TEACC in dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO) as solvent. The mechanistic aspects are discussed and a suitable mechanism has also been postulated.

Results and discussion

The oxidation of organic acids leads to the formation of carbon dioxide. The stoichiometric determination indicated the following overall reactions :

TEACC undergoes two-electron change. The oxidation state of chromium, determined by an iodometric method, was 3.95 ± 0.15 . This is in accordance with the earlier observations with structurally similar halochromates^{11,12}. It has already been shown that both PCC^{13} and PFC^{14} act as two electron oxidants and are reduced to chromium(IV) species by determining the oxidation state of chromium by magnetic susceptibility, ESR and IR studies.

Rate laws : The reactions are of first order with respect to TEACC. Further, the values of k_{obs} are independent of the initial concentration of TEACC. The reaction is first order with respect to organic acid also (Table 1). Fig. 1 depict a typical kinetic run.

Test for free radicals : The oxidation of organic acids by TEACC, in an atmosphere of nitrogen, failed to induce the polymerization of acrylonitrile. In blank experiments, with organic acid absent, no noticeable consumption of TEACC was observed. Further, the addition of acrylonitrile had no effect on the rate (Table 1). Thus a one-electron oxidation giving rise to free radicals is unlikely. To further confirm the absence of the free radicals in the reaction pathways, the reaction was carried out in the presence of 0.05 mol dm of 2,6-di-*t*-butyl-4-methylphenol (butylated hydroxytoluene or BHT). It was

Table 1. Rate constants for the oxidation of oxalic and formic acids by TEACC at 308 K

10^3 [TEACC] (mol dm ⁻³)	[Organic acid] (mol dm ⁻³)	$10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s ⁻¹)	
		Oxalic acid	Formic acid
1.00	0.10	5.25	1.50
1.00	0.20	10.6	3.05
1.00	0.40	21.4	6.21
1.00	0.60	31.0	9.36
1.00	0.80	42.3	12.4
1.00	1.00	52.2	14.4
1.00	2.00	10.8	30.6
2.00	0.20	12.6	7.20
4.00	0.20	11.3	6.15
6.00	0.20	12.2	7.56
8.00	0.20	11.6	6.62
1.00	0.40	21.0 ^a	7.29 ^a

^aContained 0.001 mol dm⁻³ acrylonitrile.**Fig. 1.** Oxidation of oxalic acid by TEACC : A typical kinetic run.

observed that BHT was recovered unchanged, almost quantitatively.

Effect of acidity : The reaction is catalysed by hydrogen ions. The hydrogen-ion dependence has the following form (Table 3).

$$k_{\text{obs}} = a + b[\text{H}^+] \quad (3)$$

The values of a and b , for oxalic acid, are $5.22 \pm 0.15 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $9.13 \pm 0.25 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ respectively ($r^2 = 0.9971$). The corresponding values for the oxidation of formic acid are $1.39 \pm 0.06 \times 10^{-3}$ and $2.58 \pm 0.10 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ ($r^2 = 0.9935$).

Kinetic isotope effect : To ascertain the importance of the cleavage of the α -C-H bond in the rate-determining step, the oxidation of α -deuterio formic acid (DFA) was studied. Results recorded in Table 2, exhibited a primary kinetic isotope effect ($k_{\text{H}}/k_{\text{D}} = 5.83$ at 298 K).

Effect of temperature : The rates of oxidation of oxalic and formic acids were determined at four different temperatures and the activation parameters were calculated (Table 2). The $\log k_2$ at different temperature is linearly related to the inverse of the absolute temperature in all cases (Fig. 2). The Arrhenius equation is, therefore, valid for these oxidations.

Effect of solvents : The oxidation of formic acid was studied in 19 different organic solvents. The choice of solvents was limited due to the solubility of TEACC and its reaction with primary and secondary alcohols. There was no reaction with the solvents chosen. The kinetics were similar in all the solvents. The values of k_2 are recorded in Table 4.

Reactive oxidising species : The observed hydrogen-ion dependence suggests that the reaction follows two mechanistic pathways, one is acid-independent and the other is acid-dependent. The acid-catalysis may well be

Table 2. Rate constants and activation parameters of the oxidation of organic acids by TEACC

Subst.	$10^4 k_2$ (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)				ΔH^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS^* (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	ΔG^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)
	288 K	298 K	308 K	318 K			
OA	12.6	26.1	52.2	10.8	51.8 ± 0.8	-121 ± 2	87.7 ± 0.6
FA	3.51	7.11	14.4	28.8	50.9 ± 0.6	-135 ± 2	90.9 ± 0.5
DFA	0.57	1.22	2.54	5.33	54.1 ± 0.6	-139 ± 2	95.3 ± 0.5
$k_{\text{H}}/k_{\text{D}}$	6.12	5.83	5.67	5.40			

Fig. 2. Oxidation of oxalic acid by TEACC : Effect of temperatures.

Table 3. Dependence of reaction rate on hydrogen ion concentration

[TEACC] = 0.001 mol dm⁻³, [Acid] = 0.10 mol dm⁻³,
Temp. = 308 K at TsOH (mol dm⁻³)

Acid (mol dm ⁻³)	0.10	0.20	0.40	0.60	0.80	1.00
	10 ⁴ k _{obs} (s ⁻¹)					
OA	60.3	72.0	90.0	104	126	144
FA	16.2	19.2	25.0	28.1	35.1	39.6

Table 4. Effect of solvents on the oxidation of formic acid by TEACC at 308 K

Solvents	10 ⁴ k ₂ (dm ⁻³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	Solvents	10 ⁴ k ₂ (dm ⁻³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)
Chloroform	51.3	Toluene	10.5
1,2-Dichloroethane	43.6	Acetophenone	56.2
Dichloromethane	47.9	THF	18.2
DMSO	144	<i>t</i> -Butyl alcohol	22.4
Acetone	30.1	1,4-Dioxane	20.0
DMF	79.4	1,2-Dimethoxyethane	11.2
Butanone	27.5	Carbon disulfide	5.25
Nitrobenzene	58.9	Acetic acid	25.7
Benzene	12.0	Ethyl acetate	14.8
Cyclohexane	1.29		

attributed to a protonation of TEACC to yield a protonated Cr^{VI} species which is a stronger oxidant and electrophile (4).

Formation of a protonated Cr^{VI} species has earlier been postulated in the reactions of structurally similar halochromates.

Solvent effect : The rate constants, k_2 , in eighteen solvents (CS₂ was not considered, as the complete range of solvent parameters was not available) were correlated in terms of the linear solvation energy relationship (5) of Kamlet *et al.*¹⁵.

$$\log k_2 = A_0 + p\pi^* + b\beta + a\alpha \quad (5)$$

In this equation, π^* represents the solvent polarity, α the hydrogen bond acceptor basicities and β is the hydrogen bond donor acidity. A_0 is the intercept term. It may be mentioned here that out of the 18 solvents, 12 have a value of zero for α . The results of correlation analyses in terms of eq. (5), a biparametric equation involving π^* and β , and separately with π^* and β are given below as eqs. (6)–(9).

$$\log k_2 = -4.16 + 1.77 (\pm 0.17) \pi^* + 0.13 (\pm 0.14) \beta + 0.33 (0.13) \alpha \quad (6)$$

$$R^2 = 0.8992; \text{sd} = 0.16; n = 18; \psi = 0.35$$

$$\log k_2 = -4.24 + 1.65 (\pm 0.19) \pi^* + 0.25 (\pm 0.16) \beta \quad (7)$$

$$R^2 = 0.8553; \text{sd} = 0.18; n = 18; \psi = 0.40$$

$$\log k_2 = -4.29 + 1.72 (\pm 0.19) \pi^* \quad (8)$$

$$r^2 = 0.8307; \text{sd} = 0.19; n = 18; \psi = 0.42$$

$$\log k_2 = -5.20 + 0.54 (\pm 0.36) \beta \quad (9)$$

$$r^2 = 0.1239; \text{sd} = 0.43; n = 18; \psi = 0.96$$

Here n is the number of data points and ψ is the Exner's statistical parameter¹⁶.

Kamlet's¹⁵ triparametric equation explains *ca.* 88% of the effect of solvent on the oxidation.

However, by Exner's¹⁶ criterion the correlation is not even satisfactory [*cf.* eq. (6)]. The major contribution is of solvent polarity. It alone accounts for 83% of the data. Both β and α play relatively minor roles.

The data on solvent effect were also analyzed in terms of Swain's equation¹⁷ of cation- and anion-solvating concept of the solvents (10).

$$\log k_2 = aA + bB + C \quad (10)$$

Here A represents the anion-solvating power of the solvent and B the cation-solvating power. C is the intercept term. $(A + B)$ is postulated to represent the solvent polarity. The rates in different solvents were analysed in terms of eq. (12), separately with A and B and with $(A + B)$.

$$\log k_2 = 1.32 (\pm 0.05) A + 1.60 (\pm 0.04) B - 3.97 \quad (11)$$

$$R^2 = 0.9939; sd = 0.04; n = 19; \psi = 0.08$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.10 (\pm 0.53) A - 2.94 \quad (12)$$

$$r^2 = 0.2024; sd = 0.43; n = 19; \psi = 0.92$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.49 (\pm 0.24) B - 3.60 \quad (13)$$

$$r^2 = 0.7022; sd = 0.26; n = 19; \psi = 0.56$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.51 \pm 0.05 (A + B) - 3.98 \quad (14)$$

$$r^2 = 0.9850; sd = 0.06; n = 19; \psi = 0.13$$

The rates of decomposition of the complex in different solvents showed an excellent correlation in terms of Swain's equation [cf. eq.(13)] with the cation-solvating power playing the major role. In fact, the cation-solvation alone account for *ca.* 70% of the data. The correlation with the anion-solvating power was very poor. The solvent polarity, represented by $(A + B)$, also accounted for *ca.* 98% of the data. In view of the fact that solvent polarity is able to account for *ca.* 98% of the data, an attempt was made to correlate the rate with the relative permittivity of the solvent. However, a plot of $\log(\text{rate})$ against the inverse of the relative permittivity is not linear ($r^2 = 0.5016$; $sd = 0.34$; $\psi = 0.73$).

Mechanism :

In view of the absence of any effect of acrylonitrile on the rate of the reaction and failure to induce the polymerization of acrylonitrile, it is unlikely that a one-electron oxidation, giving rise to free radicals, is operative in this reaction. The presence of a substantial primary kinetic isotopic effect confirmed that a α -C-H bond is cleaved in the rate-determining step. The observed solvent effect also indicated that the transition state of the reaction is more polar than the reactants.

For the formic acid oxidation, the cation-solvating power of the solvents plays a relatively more important role, supporting the preposition that an electron-deficient carbon center is formed in the transition state. Thus the transfer of a hydride-ion from the acid to the oxidant is indicated.

This hydride ion transfer may take place either via an anhydride or by an acyclic process. The involvement of a concerted cyclic process is supported by a study of the temperature dependence of the kinetic isotope effect¹⁸. The data for protio- and deuterio-formic acids when fitted in the familiar expression $k_H/k_D = A_H/A_D \exp(-\Delta H^*/RT)$ show a direct correspondence with the properties of a symmetrically transition state in which the differences in the activation energies for the protio and deuterio compounds are equal to the differences in the zero point energies of the corresponding C-H and C-D bonds (*ca.* 4.5 kJ mol⁻¹) and the entropies of the activation of the respective reactions are almost equal^{19,20}. Bordwell²¹ has documented a very cogent evidence against the occurrence of concerted one-step biomolecular processes by hydrogen transfer and it is evident that in the present studies also the hydrogen transfer does not occur by an acyclic biomolecular process. It is well established that intrinsically concerted sigmatropic reactions, characterised by transfer of hydrogen in a cyclic transition state, are the only truly symmetrical processes involving a linear hydrogen transfer²². Littler²³ has also shown that a cyclic hydride transfer, in the oxidation of alcohols by Cr^{VI}, involves six electrons and, being a Hückel-type system, is an allowed process. Thus, a transition state having a planar, cyclic and symmetrical structure can be envisaged for the decomposition of the ester intermediate. Hence, the overall mechanism is proposed to involve the formation of a chromate ester in a fast pre-equilibrium step and then a decomposition of the ester in a subsequent slow step via a cyclic concerted symmetrical transition state leading to the product (Schemes 1 and 2).

The observed negative value of entropy of activation also supports the proposed mechanism. As the charge separation takes place in the transition state, the charged ends become highly solvated. This results in an immobilization of a large number of solvent molecules, reflected in the loss of entropy²⁴.

It is of interest to compare here the mode of oxidation of organic acids by PFC²⁵, MCC²⁶ and TEACC. The oxidation by PFC presented a different kinetic picture, i.e. Michaelis-Menten type kinetics, with respect to the reductants. However, the oxidation by MCC and TEACC exhibited a first order dependence with respect to the reductants. It seems that the values of the formation cons-

Scheme 1

tants for the intermediate compound are very small in the oxidation by MCC and TEACC and is, therefore, not reflected in the rate-laws. Kinetic isotope effects, solvent effects and the dependence on the hydrogen ions are of similar nature in all these reactions, for which essentially similar mechanisms have been proposed.

Experimental

Materials : TEACC and α -deuterioformic acid (DCO₂H or DFA) were prepared by the reported methods^{6,27}. Due

to the non-aqueous nature of the medium, toluene-*p*-sulphonic acid (TsOH) was used as a source of hydrogen ions. TsOH is a strong acid and in a polar solvent like DMSO it is likely to be completely ionised. Solvents were purified by the usual methods²⁸.

Stoichiometry : To determine the stoichiometry, an excess of TEACC ($\times 5$ or greater) was reacted with the organic acid in DMSO (100 cm³) and the amount of residual TEACC after the completion of reaction was measured spectrophotometrically at 365 nm. The results indi-

Scheme 2

cated 1 : 1 stoichiometry. No quantitative determination of carbon dioxide formed was carried out. The oxidation state of chromium in completely reduced reaction mixtures.

Kinetic measurements : The reactions were followed under pseudo-first order conditions by keeping a large excess ($\times 15$ or greater) of the organic acid over TEACC. The temperature was kept constant to ± 0.1 °K. The solvent was DMSO, unless specified otherwise. The reactions were followed by monitoring the decrease in the concentration of TEACC spectrophotometrically at 365 nm for up to 80% of the reaction. No other reactant or product has any significant absorption at this wavelength. The pseudo-first order rate constants, k_{obs} , were evaluated from the linear ($r = 0.995-0.999$) plots of $\log [\text{TEACC}]$ against time. Duplicate kinetic runs showed that the rate constants were reproducible to within $\pm 3\%$.

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